

COMPETENCE IN TEACHING MAPEH IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS: BASIS FOR CAPABILITY BUILDING PROGRAM

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Competence in Teaching MAPEH in Relation to Academic Performance of Pupils: Basis for Capability Building Program

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Abstract

This study entitled Competence in Teaching MAPEH in Relation to Academic Performance of Pupils: Basis for Capability Building Program determined the relationship of the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH to academic performance of their pupils. Respondents were the one hundred twelve elementary school teachers handling MAPEH subjects; descriptive research design was used. Data were collected using the researcher-made questionnaire duly validated and tested reliable. Results revealed that most of the elementary teachers teaching MAPEH were 51 years old and above, female, have been in the service for 6-10 years, with bachelor's degree, non-MAPEH major, and attended seminars and trainings in school level. The level of competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH is high. The academic performance of pupils is very satisfactory. There was no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to age, sex, teaching position, years in service, educational attainment, specialization, and trainings attended. There was no significant relationship between the competence of teachers and academic performance of pupils.

Keywords: *academic performance, pupils, competence, teaching, MAPEH*

Introduction

To give pupils the best instruction possible and promote meaningful learning, teachers need to have a specified set of competencies (Toropova et al., 2020). According to Garcia (2019), a country's ability to succeed or fail is largely dependent on the quality of education its citizens acquire. Because a teacher's knowledge of the subject is a prerequisite for effective and substantial instruction, the teacher's performance or competency has a significant impact on the student.

According to Omar et al. (2018), teachers who possess competency are better able to support students' academic growth and development as well as help them enhance their teaching methods. This is particularly true when it comes to teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH), which is a subject taught in elementary schools to develop students' creativity, vision, and life skills.

Because all four of these components—music, the arts, physical education, and health—are linked to the growth of students' knowledge and abilities, they have a great deal of value in daily life. Students are intended to be exposed to and develop an appreciation for Western, Asian, and Philippine music through the Music and Arts Program. The value of maintaining an active lifestyle is ingrained in physical education classes. Health describes how to maintain one's physical well-being and helps teach people what they should and should not do for their bodies.

Teachers require a variety of skills and knowledge to be effective in ensuring that their pupils learn. They should serve as role models for students and facilitators of learning. As a result, they are a crucial tool for all people to acquire knowledge. Because learning is a complicated mental activity that cannot be hastened, teachers must practice a great lot to become specialists in a certain topic. Designing training programs for teachers that will provide pedagogic tools and uplift their competence will be a great help in producing more effective and efficient instruction for a quality education of the learners.

In the local setting, teaching MAPEH subjects in elementary schools has been a challenging and uphill battle for teachers who, unlike those who were graduates of MAPEH courses, may have very limited knowledge, experience, skills, competence, and exposure to handling the subject. Such has been the dilemma of MAPEH teachers whose tutelage is projected to discover future athletes, dancers, actors and actresses, singers and musicians, and artists.

It is the foregoing reasons that the researcher was motivated to conduct this study to personally ascertain the competence of elementary teachers in teaching MAPEH and how their teaching skills affect the academic performance of their pupils.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to determine the competence in teaching MAPEH of elementary teachers in the municipalities of San Enrique and Valladolid in relation to the academic performance of pupils for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of teachers teaching MAPEH in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. teaching position;

- 1.4. years in service;
- 1.5. educational attainment;
- 1.6. specialization; and
- 1.7. seminars and training attended?
2. What is the level of competence of teachers in teaching when taken as a whole and when grouped in terms of:
 - 2.1. music;
 - 2.2. arts;
 - 2.3. physical education; and
 - 2.4. health?
3. What is the academic performance of pupils when taken as a whole?
4. Is there a significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH and the academic performance of pupils?
6. Based on the results of the study, what capability building program may be introduced?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research approach, which sought to clarify current issues or challenges by gathering data that allowed for a more detailed account of the circumstances. As mentioned in Dudovskiy (2022), Fox & Bayat claim that descriptive-correlational research is frequently used to describe the characteristics and/or behaviors of the population being studied. It is a practical method of collecting information for the creation of hypotheses and linkages. This study primarily examined the relationship between teachers' competence in teaching MAPEH and pupils' academic performance.

Respondents

The subject of this study were the intermediate pupils who had MAPEH subjects at the time this study was conducted, and the respondents were 112 elementary school teachers from the Districts of San Enrique and Valladolid, in the Division of Negros Occidental handling MAPEH subjects.

This study considered all 112 elementary teachers in 17 schools in the municipalities of San Enrique and Valladolid who were handling MAPEH subjects only. The distribution of the respondents is presented in the following table.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents of the Study by School*

<i>District</i>	<i>School</i>	<i>n</i>
A San Enrique	Batuan Elem. School	6
	Don Esperedion Presbitero Elem. School	9
	Don Vicente Lopez Elem. School	5
	Eusebio R. Quitco Elem. School	6
	Guintorilan Elem. School	4
	Nasario D. Tupas Elem. School	3
	Nayon Elem. School	6
	San Enrique Elem. School	13
B Valladolid	Sibucan Elem. School	4
	Alijis Elementary School	10
	Ayungon Elementary School	3
	Batuan Elementary School	4
	Emilio Infante Elementary School	8
	Maria Palacios Presbitero Elem. School	6
	Pacol Elementary School	6
	Tabao Elementary School	9
	Valladolid Elementary School	10
Total		112

Instrument

The data-gathering instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire that aimed to determine the competence of elementary teachers in teaching MAPEH, and was composed of two parts.

Part I determined the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, teaching position, years in service, educational attainment, specialization, and MAPEH-related seminars and trainings attended.

Part II of the questionnaire assessed the teachers' competence in teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education (PE), and Health, composed of forty items answered by the respondents.

Procedure

To formally begin the research work, permission to conduct the study was obtained from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent (see Appendix B). Upon approval, copies of the letter were forwarded to the school principals of the target respondents and were provided with orientation as to the mechanics of the conduct of the study to their respective teachers. Thereafter, the researcher met with the teacher-respondents, requested their participation in the survey, and was assured that the information they would provide would be treated with complete confidentiality, and would be used for research purposes only. Parents had given their consent, through the PTA meetings, for their children to participate in the survey freely and voluntarily.

Data Analysis

At the conclusion of the survey, the data were collected, tallied and subjected to statistical treatment using appropriate statistical tools for each of the problems identified.

To answer statement of the problem 1, on teachers' age, sex, teaching position, years in service, educational attainment, specialization, and seminar and training attended, frequency count and percentage were used.

To answer statement of the problem 2, on the level of competence of elementary teachers in teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health, the mean was used.

For Problem 4, on the significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to their profile on age, teaching position, years in service, educational attainment and seminars and trainings attended, ANOVA was used. On the profile in sex and specialization, a T-test was used.

For Problem 5, on the significant relationship between the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH and the academic performance of pupils, Gamma Coefficient was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered. The data were arranged comprehensively to answer the statement of the problem using different statistical tools.

Demographic Profile of Elementary Teachers

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of elementary teachers.

Table 2. Demographic Profile of Elementary Teachers

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	25-30 years old	15	13.39
	31-35 years old	20	17.86
	36-40 years old	17	15.18
	41-45 years old	10	8.93
	46-50 years old	17	15.18
	51 years old & above	33	29.46
	Total	112	100.00
Sex	Male	12	10.71
	Female	100	89.29
	Total	112	100.0
Teaching Position	Teacher I	62	55.36
	Teacher II	15	13.39
	Teacher III	29	25.89
	Master Teacher I	6	5.36
	Total	112	100.0
Years in Service	1-5 years	19	16.96
	6-10 years	33	29.46
	11-15 years	10	8.93
	16-20 years	22	19.64
	21-25 years	16	14.29
	26 years & above	12	10.71
	Total	112	100.0
Educational Attainment	Bachelor's Degree	50	44.64

	Master's Units	42	37.50
	Master's Degree	18	16.07
	Doctoral Units	1	0.89
	Doctorate Degree	1	0.89
	Total	112	100.00
Specialization	Major in MAPEH	10	8.93
	Non-Major	102	91.07
	Total	112	100.00
Seminars and Trainings Attended	School Level	50	44.64
	District Level	40	35.71
	Division Level	18	16.07
	National Level	4	3.57
	Total	112	100.00

Table 2 reveals that in terms of age, out of one hundred twelve teacher-respondents, 33 or 29.46% are 51 years old & above, 20 or 17.85% are 31-35 years old, 17 or 15.18% are 46-50 years old, 17 or 15.18% belong to 36-40 years old group, 15 or 13.39% are 25-30 years old and 10 or 8.93 percent are 41-45 years old.

The figure above shows that most of the elementary teachers teaching MAPEH subjects belong to the 51-year-old and above group. This implies that those who belong to this age group may have been serving in the school for many years already and have acquired a wealth of knowledge, experience, and skills in performing their tasks, especially in teaching MAPEH subjects to their pupils.

The results of the 2024 study *The Effects of Age on Teachers' Self-Efficacy* by Odanga and Aloka demonstrated that teachers' self-efficacy increased with age until it reached an ideal age of 40 to 50 years, at which point it started to decline. The teachers claim that better exam performance, more experience, and better topic comprehension all lead to higher levels of self-efficacy. It then fades because of a decline in physical vitality and competing interests. The participants stated that, with respect to the domains of teacher self-efficacy, teachers' confidence in classroom management increased until middle age, when it began to wane, their confidence in instructional strategies declined, and their confidence in student engagement remained constant until middle age.

In terms of sex, there were 100 female teachers, and 12 were male teachers. The figure shows that MAPEH teachers in the 17 schools studied were largely dominated by female teachers.

Women make up a disproportionately large share of the teaching workforce. Recent statistics show that among recent Australian university graduates, women make up 68% of secondary teachers, 85% of primary teachers, and 97% of pre-primary teachers. Similarly, the proportion of female instructors in the OECD as a whole is high (theconversation.com, 2019). When teachers have a balanced gender ratio, students are exposed to both male and female role models in the classroom. However, there are significant gender differences in who enters and stays in the teaching profession: on average, women make up 70% of teachers in OECD countries, with differences depending on educational level. Female teachers are over-represented, especially at lower educational levels. In 2019, 84% of primary teachers were women, compared to 64% of secondary teachers and 44% of postsecondary teachers in the OECD. The proportion of female teachers varies significantly by country at all levels of education.

Generally speaking, the percentage of female primary and secondary school teachers in OECD countries rose marginally between 2010 and 2019 (from 83% in 2010 to 84% in 2019 and from about 63% in 2010 to 64% in 2019). Consequently, even though it is happening more slowly, the trend of rising gender disparity as described by the OECD has remained in place. Additionally, the proportion of female postsecondary teachers has grown, from 42% in 2010 to 44% in 2019 (OECD, 2021). Information about how gender inequalities may evolve in the future can be gleaned by looking at the gender distribution of teachers by age.

The percentage of female teachers in the youngest cohort in primary school fell by two percentage points between 2010 and 2019. At both the upper and lower secondary levels, the share has decreased by a percentage point. Gender ratios may start to progressively shift towards greater parity in the next years, since it looks like the pattern of widening gender gaps in elementary and secondary schooling may reverse. Since the percentage of women among new tertiary entrants has remained at 50%, the gender ratio of tertiary teachers will continue to decline.

In terms of teaching position, 62 occupied Teacher I position, 29 were Teacher III, 15 were Teacher II, and 6 were Master Teachers.

In terms of years in service, 33 or 29.46 percent of elementary teachers have served for 6-10 years, 22 or 19.64 percent for 16-20 years, 19 or 16.96 percent for 1-5 years, 16 or 14.29 percent for 21-25 years, 12 or 10.71 and 10 or 8.93 percent for 11-15 years.

In terms of educational attainment, 50 or 44.64 percent had bachelor's degrees, 42 or 37.50 percent had master's units, 18 or 16.07 percent were full-fledged master's degrees, 1 had doctoral units, and 1 was a full-fledged doctorate holder.

The training and academic qualifications of the faculty at any educational institution have a major impact on its capacity to provide high-quality instruction (Allam, 2020; Cavallone, Momunalieva et al., 2020; Pham & Nguyen, 2020; Whalley 2019; Manna & Palumbo, 2020). To ensure that students are taught by highly qualified teachers, nations all over the world have invested substantial funds and

implemented educational policies aimed at improving and assessing teacher quality (Feng and Sass, 2018). Faculty members with advanced degrees are believed to possess superior teaching competencies that directly affect students' learning, according to Tasnim, Selim, and Promi (2020). As a result, graduates will be more productive and score higher on licensure examinations.

This presumption serves as the foundation for the Civil Service Commission's (CSC) minimum educational requirement of a master's degree for professor positions at state universities and colleges (CSC Memorandum Circular No. 10, s. 2012). Some studies indicate that instructors' educational backgrounds and students' achievement in elementary and high school are positively correlated. Curry, Reeves, McIntyre, and Capps (2018) recently examined how advanced degree holders affected their academic achievement. Students performed significantly better than their peers when their teachers held a master's degree rather than a bachelor's, Curry and colleagues found.

Nevertheless, the statistics described above contradict Barnett's (2020) assertion that advanced degree-holding teachers improved their kids' scores on Mississippi's end-of-year state exams for grades three through eight. The results demonstrated the performance of pupils who were taught by professors with advanced degrees. much worse than pupils learning from teachers without such training in maths and English language arts.

In terms of specialization, 102 or 91.07 were non-MAPEH majors, and 10 or 8.93 percent were MAPEH majors.

In terms of MAPEH-related seminars and training attended, 50, or 44.64 percent attended the school level, 40, or 35.71 attended the district level, 18, or 16.07 attended the division level, and 4, or 3.57 attended the national level.

To fulfill their responsibilities as educators, teachers must constantly adapt and enhance their teaching skills (Ortega-Dela Cruz, 2020). According to Nyaaba et al. (2023), continual professional development can enhance teaching effectiveness and enhance student learning outcomes, engagement, and satisfaction. One kind of professional development program that gives faculty members a concentrated space to critically analyze, learn new skills, and exchange best practices is teaching seminars and workshops (Heron & Wason, 2023). These seminars provide a wide range of educational opportunities that address the various interests and needs of the faculty. Some offer a strong basis for teaching excellence by examining core pedagogical concepts like active learning, efficient assessment methods, and classroom management practices.

Others focus on specialized concerns, adjusting their methods to meet the demands of each business. Teachers are introduced to the latest findings in education and learning through research-focused workshops, which also help them implement evidence-based teaching practices. Technology-focused seminars increase faculty members' ability to more readily incorporate digital technologies into their lessons.

Numerous studies have found a positive correlation between teaching seminar attendance and overall teacher performance (Lizette Neng & Cheo, 2022). Instructors who participate in professional development seminars exhibit enhanced classroom management, stronger communication abilities, and a greater capacity to accommodate the various requirements of their pupils. According to research, active seminar engagement and overall teaching efficacy are positively correlated (Yoon & Kim, 2022). The results of Suryanti and Arifani's (2021) study show a positive correlation between integrated professional training and the creativity and effectiveness of Math teacher's instruction. Teachers who attend seminars for continuing professional development typically improve their classroom management, communication, and student interactions.

Level of Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH

Table 3 presents the level of competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH.

Table 3. Level of Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH

<i>Competence of Teachers</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Music	112	3.50	High
Arts	112	3.70	High
PE	112	3.88	High
Health	112	3.89	High
As a whole	112	3.74	High

Table 3 shows that the level of competence of elementary teachers in Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health are all high as indicated by the individual means of the four areas. As a whole, the level of competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH is high, as shown by the overall mean of 3.74.

Pupils who receive top-notch instruction from teachers who are very competent in teaching MAPEH do better academically and are more engaged in these topics. Pupils' attitudes towards music, the arts, physical education, and health also improve, which supports their overall growth. In addition to encouraging healthy lives, creativity, and physical fitness, competent teachers help improve the school's reputation and encourage community involvement through a variety of events and activities. All things considered, MAPEH teachers' proficiency greatly enhances pupils' learning opportunities and personal development.

The above observation conforms to the remarks of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (2018) which

underscored that since teaching performance affects student motivation, attitude, behavior, and growth in addition to the effectiveness and quality of learning, it should be taken into account. Effective teaching is based on a teacher's motivation to manage their knowledge and sufficient pedagogical skills to guide their students. Skilled educators proficiently mentor pupils during the educational journey by identifying each student's unique qualities and requirements, resulting in an ideal teaching outcome. Moreover, for teachers to regularly demonstrate their abilities, they must undergo a protracted process that involves years of practice and expertise building (Anif, Utama, and Prayitno, 2019). By recognizing each student's distinct needs and characteristics, skilled teachers effectively guide students throughout their educational journey, producing the best possible teaching results. Teachers must go through a lengthy process that includes years of experience and competence building before they can frequently display their abilities (Anif, Utama, and Prayitno, 2019).

Innovative teaching strategies must be tailored to the needs of each student and the particular classroom by effective teachers. The proper method of teaching pupils with knowledge, skills, and applications is referred to as competency (Medina & Del Rosario, 2022). Teachers need to be well-versed in a variety of competencies, such as educational, personal, social, and professional abilities, to improve student accomplishment. On the other hand, several competencies have shaped and determined educational systems and goals. Thus, evaluating the caliber of teachers is essential.

Academic Performance of Pupils

Table 4 that follows presents the academic performance of pupils.

Table 4. *Academic Performance of Pupils*

<i>Level of Academic Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	4		
Very Satisfactory	107		
Satisfactory	1	87.98	Very Satisfactory
Fairly Satisfactory	0		
Did Not Meet Expectations	0		
Total	112		

Regarding the academic performance of pupils, 107 earned a very satisfactory rating, 4 as outstanding, and 1 as satisfactory. As a whole, with an overall mean of 87.98, the performance rating of pupils was very satisfactory.

The above figure indicates that 96 percent of the pupils received a grade of very satisfactory. They may or may not have been expected to be rated outstanding, however, receiving a collective rating of very satisfactory is a legitimate measurement of the significant performance of both the pupils and the teachers.

The above finding implies that when pupils receive a very satisfactory rating in MAPEH, it demonstrates a good grasp and competency in the areas of music, the arts, physical education, and health. This shows that they have cultivated a diverse skill set and exhibit physical fitness, creativity, and health consciousness. This accomplishment may increase their self-assurance, inspire more research in these areas, and pave the way for future success in related domains.

According to Honour Society (2023), grades are a helpful way to gauge a student's proficiency in a given subject. This is because grades are one of the more objective forms of assessment. Grades can also be a helpful assessment tool for both teachers and pupils. A teacher may want to alter the way they present the relevant content if they notice that most students do poorly on a particular test.

Additionally, they might have to revise test questions or reframe a course objective. A student may need to work on their time management skills if they receive a bad grade. Or they could need help understanding things that they find challenging. Sometimes students decide they need a break from the traditional academic environment. Grades offer a straightforward way to evaluate performance and choose a course of action.

It is critical to realize that grades are not the only way to measure academic success. There might be better ways to measure success or performance in some situations. Grades can serve as a form of summative evaluation because they are cumulative. Formative assessment, however, can also support students' academic success. Discussions between teachers and students are one of the many ways that formative assessments can be conducted.

These assessments may also include email correspondence. Discussions like these can foster growth and understanding. When done properly, formative assessments can help students see learning as an ongoing process. As a result, teenagers may begin to see academic success as a process rather than a finished good (Honor Society, 2023).

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Age

Table 5 below presents the difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to age.

The table shows that out of 112 respondents, thirty-three are 51 years old and above, followed by twenty who are 31-35 years old, and nineteen who are 46-50 years old. Those who are 41-45 years old have the least number of ten.

Table 5. Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Age

Age	n	Mean
25-30 years old	15	3.70
31-35 years old	20	3.80
36-40 years old	17	3.85
41-45 years old	10	3.95
46-50 years old	19	3.50
51 years old and above	33	3.74

Computed Value (F): 1.26

p-value: 0.287

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that out of 112 respondents, thirty-three are 51 years old and above, followed by twenty who are 31-35 years old, and nineteen who are 46-50 years old. Those who are 41-45 years old have the least number of ten.

Using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the table reveals the computed value is 1.26. Comparing the p-value of .0287 shows that it is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to age.

Teachers who responded to the survey and were between the ages of 31 and 40, 41 and 50, and 50 and above scored significantly higher on the effectiveness scale than Teachers who were between the ages of 21 and 30. This was the conclusion of a study on the impact of teachers' ages on their effectiveness conducted by Rahida et al. (2018). The statistics revealed no significant differences in the group means of the other combinations. With a difference in efficacy noted between the ages of teachers, this could be seen as proof that older teachers are more effective than younger ones. They are ready to embrace the new higher-order thinking skills and are unconcerned about raising the bar for education. Older teachers may have greater life experience and be more mature, which helps them teach HOTS more successfully. Their success in implementing HOTS in the classroom may be explained by this.

Nuraini et al. (2019) and Kanto et al. (2020) assert that a teacher's age affects their experiences. Junior teachers usually don't have as much experience as senior ones. Senior teachers are also believed to be less prone to suffer from mental strain at work since they are more steady, qualified, and have a more well-rounded perspective. In the realm of politics and public discourse, it is typical to assume that there is a straightforward, linear link between a teacher's years of experience and the quality of their instruction. However, other studies identified a number of factors that defined the teachers' effectiveness and abilities and produced a unique teaching performance. At any stage of their teaching careers, less experienced educators are not always ineffective, and vice versa.

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Sex

The following table presents the difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to sex.

Table 6. Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Sex

Sex	n	Mean
Male	12	3.67
Female	100	3.75
Total	112	

Computed Value (t): -0.52

p-value: 0.605

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that out of 112 respondents, there are 100 female teachers and twelve male teachers. Using the T-Test, the table reveals the computed value is -0.52. Comparing the p-value of 0.605, it shows that it is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to sex, which can imply that both male and female teachers can be effective in teaching MAPEH subjects to their pupils.

The result of this study conforms to the statement of Manske (2021) of Marian University in Wisconsin, who stated that the teaching profession is expected to expand by at least 4% during the next 10 years at all teaching levels. According to recent data, there is still a shortage of male instructors despite the abundance of chances. It only implies that men are less inclined to teach, especially in the lower classes. One possible explanation for this could be the pervasive notion that teaching should be viewed as an extension of the job that parents perform with their children, which is still something that women do more often than males. The numerical dominance of women in education occupations, especially those aimed at the youngest children, is frequently attributed to this idea.

Additionally, the majority of music teachers are female, according to Pestaño and Ibarra's (2021) results. This implies that working with children, especially young ones, is more appealing to women than to men. Additionally, women are enrolling in education programs at a higher rate than men, which implies that women are more likely to be admitted into the area of education due to their

sheer numbers.

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Teaching Position

Table 7 that follows presents the difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to teaching position.

Table 7. *Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Teaching Position*

<i>Teaching Position</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Teacher I	62	3.75
Teacher II	15	3.68
Teacher III	29	3.79
Master Teacher I	6	3.60

Computed value (F): 0.28

p-value: 0.838

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the table reveals the computed value is 0.28. When compared, the p-value of .0838 is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to teaching position. This finding implies that effective MAPEH training may not be primarily driven by elements such as expertise level or particular responsibilities within the educational system. This suggests that other elements, such as teacher's abilities, training, and resource availability, may be more important in determining the quality of instruction. It also emphasizes how crucial it is that all MAPEH teachers, regardless of status, have fair access to professional development opportunities to guarantee consistently high-quality education.

According to statistics from schools, the most common teaching position among respondents was Teacher I. This suggests that a teacher does not necessarily need to hold a higher position in order to teach music in an elementary school. The majority of MAPEH-topic teachers hold the Teacher I position. But when it comes to teaching jobs, the Public School Teachers Magna Carta stipulates that teachers must be appropriately ranked to acknowledge that some roles demand more training and accountability than others.

As a result, either teachers did not pursue greater qualifications in order to obtain a better job, or there were still relatively few teachers promoted to higher positions as a result of a lack of funding. This suggests that there will likely be more Teacher I positions than there are other higher-level positions in the Division.

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Years in Service

Table 8 presents the difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to years in service.

Table 8. *Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Years in Service*

<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
1-5 years	19	3.90
6-10 years	33	3.66
11-15 years	10	3.92
16-20 years	22	3.68
21-25 years	16	3.74
26 years & above	12	3.70

Computed value (F): 0.786

p-value: 0.562

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the table reveals the computed value is 0.786. Comparing the p-value of .0562 shows that it is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means, there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to years in service.

The years of service of teachers did not significantly alter MAPEH teaching competency, indicating that experience may not be the main determinant of teaching quality. This can indicate that new teachers are receiving the skills they need from initial teacher training programs or that opportunities for continuous professional development are meaningful and easily accessible. It also emphasizes how crucial personal qualities of teachers—like enthusiasm, commitment, and lifelong learning—are to the success of MAPEH education.

The results of this study agree to the findings of Burroughs et al. (2019) who claimed that the length of the working period shows that instructors have different levels of experience. The success of education and the career of the teacher are both significantly influenced by experience. Due to their years of service in the teaching profession, a teacher with a long tenure history has more experience than a rookie teacher. Other research indicates that the more teaching experiences there are, the more teaching tactics are employed to promote friendly and interesting interactions between teachers and students throughout the learning process.

Evidence for this was shown by Anif, Utama, and Prayitno (2019), who claimed that knowledgeable teachers best support students in their learning process by determining each student's particular needs and characteristics. Teachers gain expertise and professionalism by honing their talents over many years of practice, which also allows them to regularly showcase their abilities. Additionally, at any point in their teaching careers, less experienced educators are not always unsuccessful, and vice versa (Kanto et al. 2020; Nuraini et al., 2019).

Instructors' education and experience, do not appear to be linked to higher productivity after the first few years. It is consistent with the previous research, which found no differences between teachers with and without experience. Other studies also shown a decline in the quality of training beyond the first three years. The aforementioned research indicates a notable discrepancy. By examining instructors' performance in the classroom according to their ages and teaching backgrounds, the current study seeks to fill the information gap.

In line with earlier studies (Fauziah et al., 2019; Pome and Feri, 2018), which did not find any connection between age or length of teaching service time and teaching performance. Those having a longer work experience will be more skilled than those who have just begun working (Pome and Feri, 2018). However, their performance will also decline as they age. Ageing is a natural part of life for an individual.

As people age, they lose part of their skills, stamina, and memory. Without the self-development tools acquired through training, education, and experiences, their quality won't improve. There was also no appreciable difference in quality between teachers with 1-3 years of experience and those with 5+ years, according to one of the few studies of its kind conducted in Australia that involved watching 80 teachers in the classroom (Graham et al., 2020). This suggests that experience may not have a significant impact on quality.

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Table 9 that follows shows the difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to educational attainment.

Table 9. *Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Bachelor's Degree	50	3.67
Master's Units	42	3.80
Master's Degree	18	3.83
Doctoral Units	1	2.93
Doctor's Degree	1	4.13

Computed value (F): 1.17
p-value: 0.327
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the table reveals the computed value is 1.17. Comparing the p-value of 0.327 shows that it is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to educational attainment.

The results of the study lend credence to the idea that faculty members with master's or doctoral degrees are more likely to support exceptional student achievement than teaching staff members with only a bachelor's degree. These results are in line with earlier studies that demonstrate that teachers with advanced degrees result in higher student success (Curry et al., 2018).

In Obeng et al.'s (2018) survey, 67 or 43.85% of the respondents held bachelor's degrees without any music units. This simply indicates that, regardless of their area of expertise, teachers are being hired according to necessity. Furthermore, a music specialist is not necessary for teaching music in elementary schools. The findings also suggest that, as the majority of respondents did not complete any music-related coursework in college, they lack prior knowledge of the fundamentals of the subject. DepEd Memorandum No. 128 series of 2006, which the Department of Education previously addressed, confirmed that a sizable portion of all Filipino music teachers lack the fundamental or required music skills and competencies. This conclusion is further supported by research by Obeng et al. (2018), which discovered that most elementary school teachers had degrees in subjects other than music. This simply suggests that having a background in music education could greatly assist teachers when it comes to teaching the subject in the classroom.

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Specialization

The following table presents differences in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to specialization.

Using the T-Test, the table reveals the computed value is 0.91. Comparing the p-value of 0.365 shows that it is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to specialization.

Given that there is no significant difference in MAPEH teaching proficiency according to specialization, a solid grounding in general pedagogy and instructional techniques may be more crucial than subject-specific knowledge. This may imply that teachers from a

variety of backgrounds may teach MAPEH successfully, either as a result of strong initial teacher preparation programs or successful chances for professional development that prioritize cross-curricular skills. It also highlights the value of creating a cooperative learning atmosphere where educators, regardless of their area of expertise, may exchange best practices and knowledge across disciplines.

Table 10. *Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Specialization*

<i>Specialization</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Major in MAPEH	10	3.89
Non-Major	102	3.73

Computed value (t): 0.91

p-value: 0.365

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

By leveraging and expanding a teacher's subject-matter expertise, subject-area specialization can increase teacher and school effectiveness (Bastian & Fortner, 2020). Subject-area specialization in primary schools has certain conceptual advantages, but it also has disadvantages. Higher student-teacher ratios and the resulting decline in student-teacher interactions are one potential disadvantage from the perspective of teacher effectiveness. Unlike self-contained courses, where teachers can develop strong relationships with fewer students by focusing on them and spending more time with them, subject-area specialization divides teachers among a greater number of students (Bastian & Fortner, 2020).

Since strong student-teacher relationships are an essential part of excellent student growth, the benefits of learning from a general classroom teacher may outweigh the benefits of specialization. The benefits and drawbacks of teacher specialization in primary schools have been discussed by educators and politicians for a century, but scientific evidence on this little-studied topic is still lacking. Although evidence of varied efficacy across subjects supports subject-area teacher specialization, recent research suggests that specialization may lead to decreased effectiveness in instruction (Fryer, 2018; Bastian & Fortner, 2018).

The inability of administrators to choose which professors should specialize in what fields may be one reason why specialization fails to live up to expectations. We show that instructors with lower value-added ratings who are not categorized as highly qualified are likely to be Indiana experts. The aforementioned study's findings are connected to a study by Uzzo, Graves, Shay, Harford, and Thompson (2018) that found that a teacher's ability to teach and explain a subject matter clearly so that students can understand its content is a key component of specialization, which leads to mastery of the subject. Teachers who possess a strong understanding of various teaching strategies and techniques can effectively design lessons by emphasizing the key points of the material with clarity.

Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Seminars and Training Attended

Table 11 presents the difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to seminars and trainings attended.

Table 11. *Difference in the Competence of Teachers in Teaching MAPEH When Grouped According to Seminars and Trainings Attended*

<i>Seminars and Trainings Attended</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>
School Level	50	3.78
District Level	40	3.67
Division Level	18	3.80
National Level	4	3.74

Computed value (F):0.38

p-value:0.771

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), the table reveals the computed value is 0.38. Comparing the p-value of 0.771, it shows that it is greater than 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to seminars and trainings attended.

Since they are in charge of providing students with experiences, knowledge, and skills, teachers are essential to the educational process both within and outside of the classroom. As a result, it is crucial in all educational systems that instructors receive the training and development necessary to fulfill the demands of the teaching profession (Aliazas et al., 2022). Teachers need to be highly skilled educators.

The Department of Education has called on the nation's schools to improve the quality of their education. Because they must stay current on curriculum, psychology, and learner pedagogy, as well as the most recent research on teaching and learning, teachers need to receive sufficient in-service training (Ayvaz-Tuncel & Cobanoğlu, 2018). The Department of Education has been regularly conducting In-Service Trainings (INSET) to enhance the skills and knowledge of teachers and school administrators.

In-service trainings, or INSET, are thought to be essential for teachers to maintain their capacity to provide excellent instruction and learning in the classroom. The primary objectives of INSET are to acquire new resources and teaching methods for a variety of subjects, expand and diversify teachers' subject-matter knowledge in a variety of learning contexts, and develop and enhance teachers' skill sets

to the degree necessary to satisfy 21st-century learning demands. In-service training is a long-term investment in teachers' professional and skill development (Janubas, 2022).

In the Philippine educational system, INSETs are held in February in the middle of the academic year and in August before the official start of the school year. Over a week, the training and activities are intended to improve the academic performance of both teachers and students. INSET's goals are to support the ongoing professional development of those employed in the educational system, encourage collaborative and participatory learning in the teaching profession, keep experts informed about new information, encourage innovative endeavours, and provide teachers—especially new teachers—with the crucial assistance they require when they take on new responsibilities or roles (Milenyo, 2022).

Training is a procedure to acquire the necessary abilities for a specific topic. The training is an effective way for teachers to improve their pedagogical abilities. A qualified teacher can apply a greater variety of abilities and approaches to help students accomplish better academically (Ulla, 2018). Students' interest in a particular subject can also be sparked by a teacher with superior teaching abilities (Giovazolias et al., 2019). Numerous scholars, such as Oliveira et al. (2019), have emphasized the significance of teacher training. The answers to issues in education are found in the training of teachers.

Few teachers have the chance or ability to attend seminars on music-related subjects, per the findings of Obeng and Senyah (2018). According to research, other subjects like physics, maths, and English have gotten more attention than music when it comes to training or seminars. Obeng and Senyah (2018) state that one of the biggest challenges to teaching music is the lack of institutional training.

Training has a significant role on a teacher's understanding of the subject matter they are teaching, according to Manila (2020). In comparison to teachers who attended little or no training at all, he continued, educators who attended more pertinent training were more likely to possess adequate understanding about the musical subject. It suggests further that teachers were able to teach the subject in the classroom despite lacking the necessary training because they were resourceful.

Relationship Between the Competence of Teachers and Academic Performance of Pupils

Table 12 on the next page presents the relationship between the competence of teachers and the academic performance of pupils.

Table 12. *Relationship Between the Competence of Teachers and Academic Performance of Pupils*

Competence of Teachers	Level of Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did not Meet Expectations	
Very Competent	0	17	0	0	0	17
Competent	3	65	1	0	0	69
Neutral	1	24	0	0	0	25
Incompetent	0	1	0	0	0	1
Total	4	107	1	0	0	112

Computed value: -0.26

p-value: 0.436

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Gamma Coefficient, the table reveals the computed value is -0.26. Comparing the p-value of 0.436, it shows that it is greater than 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant relationship between the competence of teachers and academic performance of pupils.

Training is the process of developing the skills required for a certain subject. Participating in the program is an excellent way for teachers to enhance their teaching abilities. A more seasoned teacher has a wider range of skills and strategies that can be applied to improve students' academic achievement (Ulla, 2018). Giovazolias et al. (2019) claim that a teacher with exceptional teaching abilities may also ignite students' enthusiasm in a certain subject. Many scholars have emphasized the importance of teacher preparation, including Oliveira et al. (2019). Teacher preparation offers solutions to educational problems.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are hereby presented:

Most of the elementary teachers teaching MAPEH are 51 years old and above, female, have been in the service for 6-10 years, with a bachelor's degree, non-MAPEH major, and attended seminars and trainings in the school level.

The level of competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH is high.

The academic performance of pupils is very satisfactory.

There is no significant difference in the competence of teachers in teaching MAPEH when grouped according to their age, sex, teaching position, years in service, educational attainment, specialization, and training attended.

There is no significant relationship between the competence of teachers and the academic performance of pupils.

The following recommendations are presented:

DepEd Officials can provide quality MAPEH training for teachers, enhance the curriculum, and provide resource allocation for these areas. They can identify areas where teachers need additional training or support to enhance their competence in these subjects, ensure that curricula are engaging, relevant, and aligned with current research and best practices, and advocate for the importance of music, arts, PE, and health education.

Principals can increase support to their teachers, improve curriculum that will ultimately benefit student development. They can identify areas where teachers need additional training or support to enhance their competence in teaching MAPEH, ensure that curricula are engaging, relevant, and aligned with current research and best practices, prioritize resource allocation for these subjects based on the needs identified in the study.

Teachers need to be provided with valuable insights, tools, and support to enhance their teaching practices and ultimately improve student learning experiences. They would need to adequately prepare to teach these subjects and possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and pedagogical approaches.

Parents can be provided with valuable insights into the quality of education their children are receiving. Findings of this study can empower parents to become active participants in their children's education, fostering a stronger partnership with schools and ultimately benefiting their children's overall development, encouraging them to advocate for increased funding or support for these programs within their school community.

To get the most out of MAPEH pupils should actively participate in both the theoretical and practical aspects of each subject. Engage in class discussions, ask questions, and practice the skills taught during lessons. Consistently practice music and arts techniques at home, involve yourself in physical activities outside of school, and apply health education principles to daily life. Balancing effort and enthusiasm across all areas will ensure a holistic and enriching learning experience. Moreover, they need to be provided with enhanced classroom engagement and motivation, and equipped with creative and stimulating learning environments that motivate them to participate and learn for a positive on their physical, mental, and emotional well-being.

Future researchers can conduct similar research that will improve the quality of education in these subjects, foster collaboration between researchers in different fields, such as education, psychology, and health, to address the complex challenges of teaching these subjects effectively, and advance the field of education which ensure that all students have access to a well-rounded education that prepares them for success in life.

References

- Acerro, V., Javier, E. Castro, H. (2020) Principles and Strategies of Teaching., Rex Bookstore. <https://www.rexestore.com/389-principles-of-teaching-i>
- Ahmed, K. (2022). The Importance of Music in School: Why Music Education Matters. <https://stagemusiccenter.com/music-school-blog-winchester-acton-ma/2022/8/7/the-importance-of-music-in-school-why-music-education-matters>
- Aliazas, J. V., Panoy, B. R., & Baguna, A. C. (2022). Person-Environment Fit: Empowering Leadership Practices on Teachers' Work Engagement and Motivation. In 3rd International Conference on Multidisciplinary Industry and Academic Research. Institute of Industry and Academic Research Incorporated.
- Allam, Z. (2020). Demystifying the aspect of quality in higher education: Insights from Saudi Arabia. *SAGE Open*, 10(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019899057>
- Arazo, E., Durana, M. R., Umali, A., & Almazan, R. C. (2023). Online Learning SelfEfficacy as Correlates to Academic Procrastination among Pre-Service Teachers. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*. 6(5), 171-187.
- Armstrong, P. S. (2020). Substitute Teachers during the Pandemic: Requirements, Benefits and Pay. National Council on Teachers Quality. <https://www.nctq.org/blog/Substitute-teachers-during-the-pandemic:->
- Atilano, I. (2018). Teacher's Teaching Competency, Challenges and Pupil's Academic Performance in Music: Basis For In-Service Training. A Thesis. <https://www.academia.edu/39027340/>
- Barnett, A. T. (2020). Mississippi teachers who are nationally board certified or those with advanced degrees: Effects on student achievement [Doctoral dissertation, University of Mississippi]. Retrieved from <https://egrove.olemiss.edu/etd/1803/>
- Bastian, K. C., & Fortner, C. K. (2020). Is less more? Subject-area specialization and outcomes in elementary schools. *Education Finance and Policy*, 15(2), 357-382.
- Bastian, K. C., & Janda, L. (2018). Does quantity affect quality? Teachers' course preparations and effectiveness. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 11(4), 535-558.
- Bautista, A., Yeung, J., McLaren, L. M. & Ilari, B. (2022): Music in early childhood teacher education: raising awareness of a worrisome

reality and proposing strategies to move forward, Arts Education Policy Review, DOI:10.1080/10632913.2022.2043969

Borges, A. & Richit, A. (2020). Development of Teaching Knowledge to Teach Music in Elementary School. ARTICLES, Cad. research. 50 (176) Apr-Jun 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1590/198053146782>

Brewu, J. & Adjepong, B. (2020) Alternative Approach to Teaching Music in the Primary School. European Journal of Education Studies. <https://oapub.org/edu>.

Bulger, S. M., Goc Karp, G., Kauffman, H., Li, W., & Shaffer, E. (2020). Implementing competency-based teacher education in physical education. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 39(1), 85-93.

Calosa, J. R., Andalajao, C. J., & Almazan, R. C. (2023). Social Media Use, Social Media Behavior, Cognitive Biases, and Political Awareness among Student Voters. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research* 6(5), 135-154.

Carada, I., Aliazas, J. V., Palacio, L., & Palacio, C. M. A. (2022). Perceived Skills and Employability of Senior High School Graduates: Basis for Youth Employment Policy. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*, 9(01), 6759-6766.

Carrasco, V. & Mercedes, A. (2018). Competency-based learning: Music education, the great forgotten. 4th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'18). <http://dx.doi.org/10.4995/HEAd18.2018.7473>

Cavallone, M., Manna, R., & Palumbo, R. (2020). What enables doctoral degree holders to get a job? A journey through doctoral students' satisfaction with educational services. *The TQM Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-11-2019-0268>

Cohen, J., Ruzek, E., & Sandilos, L. (2018). Does teaching quality cross subjects? Exploring consistency in elementary teacher practice across subjects. *AERA Open*, 4(3), 2332858418794492

Curry, D. L., Reeves, E., McIntyre, C. J., & Capps, M. (2018). Do teacher credentials matter? An examination of teacher quality. *Curriculum and Teaching Dialogue*, 20(1-2), 9-180

Davidova, J. (2019) Music Teacher's Competence in the 21st Century. *Pedagogika/Pedagogy* Vol.134, No. 2, pp. 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.15823/p.2019.134.6>

Dispo, G., Ducusin, M., Dulay, J., Emperador, X., & Jao, G. (2018). Finale Peer Tutorial for PreService Filipino Music Teachers. *Vision of Research in Music Education* Vol. 32 Article 10. <https://opencommons.uconn.edu/vrme/vol32/iss/10>

Feng, L., & Sass, T. R. (2018). The impact of incentives to recruit and retain teachers in "hard-to-staff" subjects. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 37(1), 112-135. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pam.22037>

Flipovic, S., (2018). The role of basic and specific competencies in the teaching of fine art in Serbia. <http://www.cyberleninka.ru>

Fryer Jr, R. G. (2018). The "pupil" factory: Specialization and the production of human capital in schools. *American Economic Review*, 108(3), 616-56.

Gagnon, S. G., Huelsman, T. J., Kidder-Ashley, P., & Lewis, A. (2019). Preschool student–teacher relationships and teaching stress. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 47(2), 217-225.

Gandonu, S. P., Azeez, O., Aderinto, O. Oridola, A., (2019). Employing Corporal Punishment in Management of Visual Art Classin Lagos State Senior Secondary Schools: Challenging the Oppressive Pedagogy. *Nigerian Education Review*, 12(1),209- 220.

Garcia, Jr. A. (2019). BSED-MAPEH Students' Reflections on their Academic & Skills Competencies, Perceived Body Images, Self-Esteem Inventory & Comfortability in Social Situations On Becoming a Teacher. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. Vol. 7, No. 4, Part IV, November 2019.

Gene, S. K., and Acquah E. O. (2021) Instructional Materials for Teaching Performing Arts in WA Municipality, Ghana. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Development Psychology*. Volume 4, Issue 2, 2021 (pp. 43-63) <https://doi.org/10.52589/BJELDP-1XIBV8FD>

Ghozali, I. (2020) Professional Competence of Teachers in Learning Music at Elementary Schools in Pontianak. *Harmonia: Journal of Arts Research and Education*.

Gil, D., Alzugararay, F., Casanova, O., & Orejudo, S. (2021). A Scale to Measure Educators' Musical Skills in Early Childhood Education. *Sun Direct Journals and Books*.

Gråstén, A., Yli-Piipari, S., Huhtiniemi, M., Salin, K., Hakonen, H., & Jaakkola, T. (2021). A one-year follow-up of basic psychological need satisfactions in physical education and associated in-class and total physical activity. *European Physical Education Review*, 27(3), 436-454.

Guo, Z. and Liu, S. (2021). Exploring Key Competencies and Professional Development of Music Teachers in Primary Schools in the Era of Artificial Intelligence <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/5097003>

- Heron, M., & Wason, H. (2023). Developing dialogic stance through professional development workshops. *Innovations in education and teaching international*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2271892>
- Hill, A. J., & Jones, D. B. (2018). A teacher who knows me: The academic benefits of repeat student-teacher matches. *Economics of Education Review*, 64, 1-12.
- Julia, J., Iswara P., Gunara S., Yildiz, Y., & Agustian, E. (2020). Developing Elementary School Teacher Competence in Making Music Learning Media Using Scratch Application: An Action Research. <https://ejournal.upi.edu/index.php/mimbar>
- Juraboev, B. & Mamadiyurova, K. (2022). Principles of Teaching and Ways to Implement Them. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*. <http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=22230>
- Kiilu, K., Laanemets, U. & Ruubel, K. (2020). Skills For Creating Supportive Learning Environments – An Essential Component of Teachers` Professional Competence. *Research Gate*. <http://DOI:10.17770/sie2020vol3.4950>
- King, F. (2018). Music Delivered by Primary School Generalist Teachers in Victoria: Informing Teaching Practice. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(5) Research Online. <https://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v43n5.4>
- Laidlaw, J. (2022). An Action Research Study to Enhance a Music Teacher`s Creative Pedagogies with Children. *Canadian Journal of Action Research*
- Li, C., Wang, J., & Wu, Y. (2019). Teacher competency and physical literacy development among secondary school students: A multilevel mediation model. *European Physical Education Review*, 25(1), 82-98. 19) Li, C., Wang, L., & Wang, J. (2018). Physical education teacher self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and teacher-student relationship: A moderated mediation model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1428.
- Lizette Neng, S., & Cheo, N. (2022). The effect of teachers` participation in seminars on their teaching effectiveness in secondary schools in Tubah Sub Division. *Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences*, 178-191. <https://procedia.online/index.php/philosophy/article/view/272>
- Lorenzo R. M., (2022). Music education models in the 21st Century, The music mediation model for social engagement *Revista Educación*, vol. 46, no. 2, 2022 Universidad de Costa Rica, Costa Rica. <https://doi.org/10.15517/revedu.v46i2.49922>
- Manila, B. M. (2020). Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Music Education among Public Elementary Teachers. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, Volume 2, Issue 3, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3690086
- Manske, P. (2021). Male Teachers Play an Important Role in the Future of Education. *Marian University Wisconsin*. <https://www.marianuniversity.edu/news/importance-of-male-teachers-future-of-education/>
- Mocheche, E. K., Raburu, P. A. & Bosire, J. (2018). Is Marital Status a Predictor of Job Satisfaction of Public Secondary School Teachers? *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences* 2018, 8(3): 51-58 <http://journal.sapub.org/ijpbs>
- Mockler, N. (2020). Teacher professional learning under audit: Reconfiguring practice in an age of standards *Professional Development in Education*. 10.1080/19415257.2020.1720779
- Momunalieva, A., Urdaletova, A., Ismailova, R., & Abdykeev, E. (2020). The quality of higher education in Kyrgyzstan through the eyes of students. *Quality in Higher Education*, 26(3), 337-354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2020.1790122>
- Mufida, N., Arafat, Y. & Puspita, Y. (2021). The Effect of Training and Teaching Experience on Teacher`s Performance. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, volume 565. <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>.
- Murungi, C.G., Wambua, M.M., & Mutwiri, C. (2018). Physical facilities and strategies used by teachers to improve pupils` performance in social studies in Makueni County, Kenya. *International Journal of Pregnancy & Childbirth Research Article*. <http://medcraveonline.com>
- MusicCultEduc_31_125.pdf.
https://ir.lib.hiroshimau.ac.jp/files/public/4/47395/20190411112637185946/MusicCultEduc_31_125.pdf
- Nyaaba, R. A., Abdul-Gafaar, S., Akulga, C. A., & Kwakye, D. O. (2023). Assessing the impact of continuous professional development of teachers and its effects on satisfaction, achievement, and engagement: Colleges of Education, Northern Ghana. *Journal of Education and Teaching Methods*, 2(2), 41-57. <https://doi.org/10.58425/jetm.v2i2.178>
- Obeng, P. & Senyah, E. O. (2018) The Challenges of Music Teaching and Learning in Primary Schools in Offinso South Municipality. *Journal of Education and Practice*. ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.9, No.27s, <https://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JEP/article/viewFile/44257>
- Odonuga, A.F. (2019). Towards Music Teachers Competence on Students' Academic Achievement: Frameworks for Assessing Music Teaching and Learning. *Adeyemi Federal University of Education* <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336408777>

- OECD (2021), *Education at a Glance 2021: OECD Indicators*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/b35a14e5-en>
- Olanrewaju, A., Elongonye, M., & Osuji, J. N. (2020). Impact of Physical Facilities on School Effectiveness in Kwara State Public Secondary Schools, Nigeria. *Al-Hikmah Journal of Educational Management and Counselling*, Vol. 2 (1), June 2020. <https://alhikmah.edu.ng/AJEMC/index.php/ajemc/article/view/56>
- Olasehinde-Williams, F., Lasiele, Y. & Owolabi, H., (2018). Teachers' Knowledge Indices as Predictors of Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Kwara State, Nigeria. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 6(1), 73-90.
- Ortega-Dela Cruz, R.A. (2020). Pedagogical practice preferences among generational groups of learners: Towards effective twenty-first century higher education. *Journal of University Teaching & Learning Practice*, 17 (5), 1-19. <https://ro.uow.edu.au/jutlp/vol17/iss5/6/>
- Ovcharenko, N., Merezhko, Y., Moskva, O., Neboga, O., & Kosiak, L. (2021). Technological Competence of Future Music Teachers: Diagnostic and Formative Methods. *Amozonia Investiga*, 10(48), 238-247. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2021.48.12.25>
- Panergayo, A. A. E., & Aliazas, J. V. C. (2021). Students' Behavioral Intention to Use Learning Management System: The Mediating Role of Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 11(11).
- Parson, L., Childs, B., & Elzie, P. (2018). Using competency-based curriculum design to create a health professions education certificate program the meets the needs of students, administrators, faculty, and patients. *Health Professions Education*, 4(3), 207- 217.
- Pestaño, R. & Ibarra, F.P. (2021). Pedagogical Competencies and Classroom Anxieties in Teaching General Music. Vol. 5 No. 1 (2021): *IRJE | Indonesian Research Journal in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.22437/irje.v5i1.12098>
- Pestaño, R. & Ibarra, F.P. (2021). Pedagogical Competencies and Classroom Anxieties in Teaching General Music. Vol. 5 No. 1 (2021): *IRJE | Indonesian Research Journal in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.22437/irje.v5i1.12098>
- Pham, H. T., & Nguyen, C. H. (2020). Academic staff quality and the role of quality assurance mechanisms: The Vietnamese case. *Quality in Higher Education*, 26(3), 262-283. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2020.1761603>
- Pulimeno M, Piscitelli P, De Marco E, Colazzo S. Narrative-based strategies to promote healthy eating behaviours in childhood: a systematic review. *MeTis - Mondì educativi. Temi, indagini, suggestioni*. 2018;8(1):184–220. doi: 10.30557/mt000015.
- Rahida Aini Mohd Ismail, Rozita Arshad, Zakaria Abas (2018). Can Teachers' Age and Experience influence Teacher Effectiveness in HOTS? *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Social Science & Innovation (IJASSI)* eISSN: 2600-7746 2018, Vol. 2, No. 1
- Rosmaria Omara, Nor Aniza Ahmada, Siti Aishah Hassana, Samsilah Roslan (2018). Importance Of Teachers' Competency Through Students' Perception In Relationships Between Parental Involvement And Motivation With Students' Achievement. 10: 3-3 (2018) 17–23 | www.sainshumanika.utm.my | e-ISSN ISSN: 2289-6996
- Semaka, J. (2020). An Integral Approach to the Meaning of Competence. *Vilnius University Open Series* 3:120-135. <http://doi:10.15388/SRE.2020.11>.
- Silvestre, M. & Itaas, E. (2020). Lived Experiences of Teachers Teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health: Implications to Graduate Education. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology* <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT20DEC053.pdf>
- Soykunt, N. & Gorgoretti, B. (2019) Views of Music Teachers on Psycho-Motor Activities. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*. <http://doi:10.7596/taksad.v8i1.1769>
- Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers*. AscD.
- Sungurtekin, S. (2021). Classroom and Music Teachers' Perception about the Development of Imagination and Creativity in Primary Music Education. *Journal of Pedagogical Research* Volume 5, Issue 3. <http://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.2021371364>
- Suryanti, S., & Arifani, Y. (2021). The relationship between blended mathematics professional training and teachers' creativity and effectiveness. *International journal of instruction*, 14(2), 139-154. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1291124>
- Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Development and Validation of a Philippine Music Achievement Test in Addressing the K to 12 Music Curriculum Learning Competencies. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, Vol. 9, No. 4, pp. 16-25. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3719507
- Tasnim, M., Selim, I., & Promi, S. M. (2020). Effectiveness of faculty development program and its impact on student-centered learning outcome in private universities of Bangladesh. *Journal of Talent Development and Excellence*, 12(1), 3684-3694.
- Toropova, A., Myrberg, E & Johansson, S., (2020). Teacher job satisfaction: the importance of school working conditions and teacher characteristics, *Educational Review*, DOI: 10.1080/00131911.2019.1705247

Tumapon, T. T. (2022). Problems: Music Education online. *The Manila Times*. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2022/03/31/campus-press/problems-music-education-online/1838304>

Uktamovna, M. D. (2021). Pedagogical Skills of a Music Teacher Organizing And Conducting A Lesson. *International Engineering Journal for Research & Development*. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/V4CP5>

UNESCO, (2018). *Guidebook on Education for Sustainable Development for educators - Effective teaching and learning in teacher education institutions in Africa*. Paris: UNESCO.

UNESCO. Education 2030: Incheon Declaration and Framework for Action for the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goal 4. Available from: http://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/education-2030-incheon-framework-for-action-implementation-of-sdg4-2016-en_2.pdf. Accessed 10 March, 2019.

United Nations Development Group. "Together Possible: Gearing up with 2030 Agenda." Available from: <https://undg.org/document/together-possible-gearing-up-for-the-2030-agenda>. Accessed 10 March, 2019.

Uosukainen, H., Viira, A., & Ojala, J. (2018). Physical education teacher competencies and student motivation. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 23(4), 385-400.

Uzzo, S. M., Graves, S. B., Shay, E., Harford, M. & Thompson, R. (2018). *Pedagogical content knowledge in STEM*. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing AG.

Villanueva, M. A. (2019). Difficulties Encountered by Grade 5 Pupils in Learning Rhythm. A Course Paper. <https://www.academia.edu/4040614>

Walling, D. & Davis, J., 2020. *School, Preparation of Teachers*. <http://www.education.stateuniversity.com>

Webster, P. R. (2018). Video Views: Music Is My Passion, Part 1. *National Association for Music Education*. Volume 105, Issue 2 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0027432118809355>

Whalley, W. B. (2019). Towards institutional 'quality education' policies in higher education: A schema for their implementation. *Quality in Higher Education*, 25(3), 340-358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2019.1684041> Will, M. (2018, August 22). Teachers in Kentucky no longer have to earn a master's degree. *Education Week*. Retrieved from http://blogs.edweek.org/edweek/teacherbeat/2018/08/teachers_kentucky_no_longer_earn_masters_degree.html?

World Health Organization. Definition of Health. Accessed 2 April 2019. Available from: <https://8fit.com/lifestyle/the-world-health-organization-definition-of-health/>.

Yoon, I., & Kim, M. (2022). Dynamic patterns of teachers' professional development participation and their relations with socio-demographic characteristics, teacher self-efficacy, and job satisfaction. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 109, 103565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103565>

Zulueta, L., & Panoy, J. F. (2022). Scenario-Based Microlearning Strategy for Improved Basic Science Process Skills in Self-Directed Learning. *International Journal of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics*, 2(4), 54-73.

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